

Preventable

SUSTAINABLE CARE FOR RARE TUMOUR RISK SYNDROMES

Abstract Book for the PREVENTABLE Mid-Term Conference

3rd October 2024

Pathé Docks 76, Rouen, France

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the European Union

INVITE SPEAKERS

Adriana Costal – ICO, Spain: Session 1 (09:35 – 09:50)

“Not such a rare syndrome: uncovering the prevalence of Birt-Hogg-Dubé (BHD)”

No abstract available

Andrew Titman – Lancaster University, UK: Session 2 (11:25 – 11:40)

“Developing a modelling framework for cost-effectiveness modelling of Rare-Tumour Risk Syndrome”

Cost-effectiveness modelling in Rare-Tumour Risk Syndromes (RTRS) presents particular challenges. Most prominently, by their very nature, the number of known carriers for each RTRS is limited and therefore the sample sizes of available datasets are small. Available data on the life history of carriers is prone to ascertainment bias and any direct evidence on the effectiveness of surveillance programmes is observational in nature. Additionally, modelling is complicated by the complexity of RTRS, with some syndromes associated with elevated risks of multiple different cancer tumour types often with very different age and gender specific onset rates, and with considerable patient (or family)-level heterogeneity.

The talk will summarize the findings of systematic literature reviews of the eight RTRSs involved in PREVENTABLE and how it influences the planned strategies for estimation and evidence synthesis of the key parameters of the health economic models. The proposed modelling structure, including the parameterization of preventative treatment effects and the accommodation of multiple cancer types, will be outlined.

Marta Marques – UNL, Portugal: Session 3 (15:35 – 15:50)

“Improving communication in healthcare: the role of behavioural science”

No abstract available

Nunos Marcos – Ipatimup, Portugal: Session 3 (16:05 – 16:20)

“Creating outreach materials for 8 Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes”

It is estimated that only around 20-30% of people with rare tumour risk syndromes (RTRS) have been diagnosed to date, and many carriers and asymptomatic patients from families with these syndromes, if left untested or undiagnosed, develop particularly aggressive cancers, leading to premature death. Given the rarity that characterizes these RTRS, and the specificities of their biology and clinical management, an increased visibility and awareness is paramount.

For this objective we have designed a segmented outreach program that aims to 1) help at-risk individuals make better informed decisions, 2) raise awareness and knowledge on the medical community of GPs or family physicians, and 3) contribute to better management policies with health decision-makers. This program will involve the creation of a diverse set of audio&visual contents for different target groups about 8 different RTRS, ranging from infographic videos, to documentaries, videocasts with experts, and a website, involving patients, family members, clinical and research specialists, recorded on location in 6 countries, along with written information, using the most up-to-date scientific literature and state-of-the art audiovisual techniques.

This program is currently underway, with the review of scientific literature and the concept design and development stages already completed, the filming for 3 syndromes completed (in Portugal, Spain and Netherlands) and the 4th underway (in France), editing and post-production of 16 videos finalized and 7 in progress, and a website production underway.

A selection of the finalized outputs will be presented in this meeting and a dissemination plan will be discussed with the partners.

ABSTRACT INFORMATION

Submitted by	Birte Lundhaug & Hildegunn Vetti
email	birte.christine.blindheim.lundhaug@helse-bergen.no
Submission Objective	Abstract submitted for Preventable – Midterm Conference – October 3 2024

CANCER PREVENTION VERSUS CANCER TREATMENT IN FAMILIAL MALIGNANT MELANOMA – PRESENTATION OF COSTS IN PARALLEL PATHWAYS OF CARE

Birte Lundhaug¹, Ingeborg M Bachmann^{2,3}, Rita Grude Ladstein^{2,3}, Oddbjørn Straume^{4,5}, Jurgita Januleviciute Gangstoe⁶, Marianne Tveit Haavind¹, Cathrine Bjorvatn^{1,7}, Hildegunn Høberg Vetti^{1,7}

1Western Norway Familial Cancer Center, Department of Medical Genetics, Haukeland University Hospital, Bergen, Norway; 2Department of Dermatology, Haukeland University Hospital, Bergen, Norway; 3Department of Clinical Medicine, University of Bergen, Bergen, Norway; 4Department of Oncology and Medical Physics, Haukeland University Hospital, Bergen, Norway; 5Department of Clinical Science, University of Bergen, Bergen, Norway; 6Department of Finance, Haukeland University Hospital, Bergen, Norway; 7Faculty of Health Studies, VID Specialized University, Bergen, Norway

Abstract (3000 characters maximum):

Problem to be solved:

CDKN2A and CDK4 are the main genes for familial malignant melanoma. Pathogenic variants in these genes are associated with a high lifetime risk of developing melanomas, as well as an increased risk of pancreatic cancer. Through regular dermatological surveillance and early diagnosis, premalignant skin lesions can be detected and removed, thereby reducing the risk of advanced cancer. No previous study has investigated the medico-economic benefits of implementing surveillance versus cancer treatment for patients with rare tumour risk syndromes in Europe.

Objective:

Within the framework of the European PREVENTABLE consortium, we aim to investigate the significance of specialized healthcare for individuals with familial malignant melanoma.

Methodology:

Based on clinical experience and multidisciplinary expertise, we have identified parallel pathways of care for patients with familial malignant melanoma. We have developed a matrix that describes all consultations and clinical sub-procedures that are part of the various treatment trajectories. Treatment costs are calculated using diagnosis-related groups (DRGs) that reflect the average cost of the treatment provided. Costs related to lab, radiology and pathology are estimated based on public reimbursement categories. Necessary approvals from ethical research

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committees have been obtained, allowing the matrix to be validated with clinical data from all European centers involved in the PREVENTABLE consortium.

Results:

For patients with familial malignant melanoma, we have identified 95 sub-procedures, categorized under 26 different clinical consultations and procedures. Together they constitute six modules/protocols including genetic diagnosis, risk assessment, surveillance, treatment of early stage and advanced cancer, and post-treatment follow-up.

Conclusion:

The matrix of subprocedures and related costs will make it possible to compare treatment costs across different pathways of care, such as costs of regular dermatological surveillance versus treatment for malignant melanoma at an early or advanced stage.

Instructions

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- Define all non-standard abbreviations at first use;
- No figures or tables can be included;
- An additional section for acknowledgements can be added to the body (included in the character count)

ABSTRACT INFORMATION

Submitted by	Carolina Betiana Di Fabrizio
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Submission Objective	Abstract submitted for Preventable – Midterm Conference – October 3 2024

[RARE TUMOUR RISK SYNDROMES, MODELLING THE NATURAL PROGRESSION: A SCOPING REVIEW]

[Carolina Di Fabrizio¹; Judite Gonçalves¹; Zillur Shabuz²; Andrew Titman²; Ceu Mateus³]

[1: Health Economics & Management Knowledge Center, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, School of Business and Economics, Lisbon, Portugal.

2: Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Lancaster University, Bailrigg, Lancaster, UK.

3: Division of Health Research, Lancaster University, Bailrigg, Lancaster, UK.]

Abstract (3000 characters maximum):

Of the 18 million new cancer cases diagnosed each year, hereditary cancer syndromes are estimated to account for nearly 10%, despite often being underdiagnosed. To date, more than 40 distinct types of hereditary cancer syndromes have been identified. Most of them affect 5 per 10.000 people or less and are known as “rare tumour risk syndromes” (RTRS). Although individually considered rare, together they encompass a significant number of patients who face common challenges: delayed diagnosis, limited preventive measures and therapeutic mismanagement.

Even though there is an abundance of information regarding diagnosis and treatment, data on the natural history of the disease that could be used for future studies in health economics is insufficient. This review aims to retrieve information to inform and define the modelling of costs and outcomes for RTRS patients, while providing a ground for future economical analysis.

Systematic literature searches were performed between March and August, 2024. PubMed and Embase were searched to identify relevant studies about 8 RTRS (Birt Hogg Dube, Familial Melanoma, Familial GIST, Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer, Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and renal cell cancer, Li Fraumeni and Hamartoma Tumour Syndrome), their natural history, cancer risks and surveillance programs, including both symptomatic and asymptomatic patients. Studies published between 2010 and 2024 were considered and those regarding treatment or diagnosis, single cases reports or reviews were excluded.

After screening 12751 titles and abstracts, 69 studies fulfilled the inclusion criteria and were selected for this review. The search yielded mostly retrospective cohort studies (n=46, 67%) followed by prospective studies (n=20, 29%) and were mainly from European or American countries.

All studies reported the number of patients included, with a mean of 179 individuals, ranging from 12 to 702, with a higher presence of female participants (mean: 73%).

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Regarding age at different diagnosis, data found was mostly concerning age of first tumour (n=42, 61%) whereas only 18 studies (26%) reported age at RTRS diagnosis, usually occurring after the cancer diagnosis.

The evidence found was mainly related to cancer incidence (n=47, 68%) and overall prognosis (n=30, 43%), while life cumulative risk of cancer was the least reported outcome, with over 63% of the references not mentioning it. Although most studies describe proposed clinical surveillance strategies, less than half of them (n=30, 43%) apply the described strategies to their own cohorts.

Researchers working on models of these diseases, for economic evaluation or other purposes, may use these findings as their starting point. While there is adequate information regarding cancer incidence and cumulative cancer risk, further research including clinical surveillance is needed. Among the syndromes, hereditary GIST has the least available information, highlighting a greater need for extra research.

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ABSTRACT INFORMATION

Submitted by	Celina São José
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Submission Objective	Abstract submitted for Preventable – Midterm Conference – October 3 2024

DECODING CDH1: THE HIDDEN ROLE OF REGULATORY NONCODING SEQUENCES IN HEREDITARY DIFFUSE GASTRIC CANCER

Celina São José 1,2; Marta Ferreira 1,3, Lilian Cordova 4; Ana Pedro 1; Ana André 1; José Garcia-Pelaez 1; Janine Senz 4; Pardeep Kaurah 4; Fiona Puntieri 2, Juliane Glaser 2; David Huntsman 4,7,8; Stefan Mundlos 2,5,6; Kasmintan Schrader 4; Carla Oliveira 1,9

1 Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

2 Max Planck Institute for Molecular Genetics, Berlin, Germany

3 Dept. Computer Science, Faculty of Science, University of Porto

4 Department of Pathology and Laboratory Medicine, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada

5 Institute of Medical and Human Genetics, Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Berlin, Germany

6 Berlin-Brandenburg Center for Regenerative Therapies (BCRT), Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Berlin, Germany

7 Department of Molecular Oncology, British Columbia Research Institute, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada

8 Genetic Pathology Evaluation Centre, University of British Columbia and Vancouver General

9 Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

Abstract (3000 characters maximum):

Background: CDH1 or CTNNA1 germline inactivation explains 10-40% of families with hereditary diffuse gastric cancer (HDGC). Missing heritability in over half of HDGC-suspected families prevents proper management and disease prevention. We hypothesized that defects in CDH1-regulatory elements contribute to HDGC missing heritability.

Methods: We called single-nucleotide/copy-number variants (SNV/CNV) from 19 HDGC probands from whole-genome sequencing data, performed gene-ontology analysis, 4C-seq and ATAC-seq in normal stomach epithelia, CRISPR-Cas9, RT-PCR and flow cytometry in cell lines, RT-PCR, immunohistochemistry and microsatellite instability (MSI) analysis in tumours and enhancer reporter assays in mouse embryos.

Results: We crossed ATAC-seq (46.249 peaks) and 4C-seq (370 CDH1 promoter interactor-sequences) data from normal stomach epithelia with WGS data (1.882 rare CNVs) from 19 HDGC-suspected families and obtained a CDH3 20kb-deletion and a 39bp-intergenic deletion downstream of CDH1. The CDH3 deletion was mimicked with CRISPR-Cas9 (homozygous) triggering complete CDH1 mRNA/protein downregulation, similarly to a CDH1 coding deletion. Two sequences within the CDH3 CNV triggered 50% CDH1 mRNA/protein downregulation and enhancer activity in mouse embryos. Tumour displayed CDH1/E-cadherin

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expression loss, arguing towards the causality of this deletion. CRISPR-Cas9 homozygous clone mimicking the intergenic deletion triggered half CDH1 mRNA/protein downregulation. Variants in genes causing gastrointestinal tumour risk syndromes revealed a MLH1 2.7Kb germline deletion in a family presenting DGC alone. This deletion overlaps a stomach-specific regulatory element. Gastric tumour displayed MLH1 mRNA reduced expression, MLH1 protein loss and MSI, proving causality of this variant. Gastric tumour also shows reduced CDH1 mRNA expression, arguing towards the role of the stomach-specific regulatory element in DGC aetiology in this family. CRISPR-Cas9 mimicking the family deletion (heterozygous) triggered half expression of MLH1 and CDH1/E-cadherin mRNA and protein. Combined analysis of deleted accessible chromatin regions revealed a pattern of impaired immune-related pathways in additional 9 families.

Conclusion: We identified regulatory regions within the CDH1 topologically-associated domain and within a MLH1 stomach-specific regulatory sequence, that harbour CNVs potentially explaining the missing heritability in three HDGC-suspected families. Germline CNVs in stomach regulatory regions favouring an immune-deficient phenotype may predispose 9 additional families to HDGC.

Funding: FCT: PTDC/BTM-TEC/30164/2017, PTDC/BTM-TEC/6706/2020, SFRH/BD/140796/2018; EU: SOLVE-RD_Ref 22184, HORIZON_HORIZON-HLTH-2022-CARE-08.

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ABSTRACT INFORMATION

Submitted by	Daniel Ferreira
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Submission Objective	Abstract submitted for Preventable – Midterm Conference – October 3 2024

A NOVEL BIOMIMETIC TOOL TO STUDY DISEASE INITIATION OF DEADLY HEREDITARY DIFFUSE GASTRIC CANCER SYNDROME

Daniel A. Ferreira^{1,2}, Rita Barbosa-Matos^{1,2,3}, Luzia Garrido^{4,5}, Ana C. Brito^{1,2,3}, João Fonseca^{1,2,3}, Silvana Lobo^{1,2,3}, Ana Moutinho^{1,2,6}, Alexandre Dias^{1,2,3}, Irene Gullo^{1,4,5}, Ana Mamede^{1,2}, Mengwei Yang⁷, Aldana G. Gojanovich⁷, Renata Oliveira^{4,5}, João Parente Freixo⁸, Pedro Louro^{9,10}, Ana Rita Ferreira Pacheco Quental^{4,5}, Ana Grangeia^{4,5}, Hugo Pinheiro^{1,2,11}, Peter Ertl¹², Pedro L. Granja¹, Susana Fernandes⁵, Fátima Carneiro^{1,4,5}, Sérgio Castedo^{1,4,5}, Gustavo Mostoslavsky⁷, Carla Oliveira^{1,2,5}
(1) i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal, (2) Ipatimup – Institute of Molecular Pathology and Immunology, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal, (3) ICBAS - Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas Abel Salazar, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal, (4) CHUSJ, Centro Hospitalar e Universitário de São João, Porto, Portugal, (5) Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto, Porto, Portugal, (6) CHUP, Centro Hospitalar Universitário do Porto, Porto, Portugal, (7) Center for Regenerative Medicine (CRoM), Boston University School of Medicine, Boston, United States, (8) Center for Predictive and Preventive Genetics, Institute for Molecular and Cell Biology, Porto, Portugal, (9) Medical Genetics Service, Centro Hospitalar Universitário de São João, Porto, Portugal, (10) Faculty of Health Sciences, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal, (11) Department of Internal Medicine, Centro Hospitalar Tâmega e Sousa, Paredes, Portugal, (12) Faculty of Technical Chemistry, Vienna University of Technology (TUW), Vienna, Austria

Abstract (3000 characters maximum):

Background/Objectives: Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (HDGC), caused by CDH1 loss of function, can only be prevented with prophylactic removal of stomach and breasts. The growing number of prophylactic surgeries hamper the study of disease initiation. Herein, we present the development of a biomimetic HDGC model combining organ-on-a-chip technology with patient-derived induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) to overcome the lack of patients' target organs.

Methods: We developed a microfabrication methodology based on xurography to engineer a functional stomach-on-a-chip, which was tested for biomimetic stretching capability and structural integrity. This was characterized with immuno-fluorescence, enzymatic, and trans-epithelial transport assays. Patients' blood samples were collected for the establishment of a biobank of HDGC families with peripheral mononuclear blood cells (PBMCs) and its derived iPSCs. iPSCs were obtained using the Sendai virus integration-free method.

Results: We designed and fabricated a stomach-on-a-chip device emulating the 3 inner gastric

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layers and recapitulating gastric peristaltic-like motion, intraluminal-flow, cell polarization, barrier function, pepsin activity, and the gastric lumen. We also established and characterized iPSCs from 9 patient-derived PBMCs, which were validated for pluripotency and further differentiated into stomach organoids. The stomach-on-a-chip is ready to be populated with HDGC patient-derived organoids.

Conclusion: We created a functional stomach-on-a-chip that can be produced in a few hours, and a unique infrastructure that will allow recreating organs that no longer exist from HDGC patients submitted to life-saving prophylactic surgery. This is a pioneer model to study early diagnosis and treatment in HDGC.

Funding:Researcher/Horizon_Europe/i3S/2311/2022; DETONATEProject/2022.02951.PTDC

Keywords: Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer, Organoids, Organ-on-a-chip

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ABSTRACT INFORMATION

Submitted by	João Abel Fonseca
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Submission Objective	Abstract submitted for Preventable – Midterm Conference – October 3 2024

FOLLOW-UP FINDINGS IN PORTUGUESE HEREDITARY DIFFUSE GASTRIC CANCER FAMILIES: RELEVANT CLINICAL INFORMATION AND SURGICAL OUTCOME ASSESSMENT FROM SURVEILLANCE AND PROPHYLACTIC INTERVENTIONS

Fonseca, J.*1; Barbosa-Matos, R.*1; Garrido, L.*2; Mamede, A.2; Oliveira, R.3; Freixo, J.4; Louro, P.3; Quental, R.3; Grangeia, A.3; Pinheiro, H.1; Fernandes, S.2; Carneiro, F.1; Castedo, S.1; Gullo, I.1; Oliveira, C.1

1i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Universidade do Porto 2CHUSJ – Centro Hospitalar e Universitário de São João 3Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto 4Center for Predictive and Preventive Genetics, Institute for Molecular and Cell Biology

Abstract (3000 characters maximum):

Background: Individuals diagnosed with hereditary diffuse gastric cancer (HDGC) often carry CDH1 germline variants, and current risk reduction measures involve prophylactic removal of stomachs and breasts. For diffuse gastric cancer (DGC), recent lifetime risk estimates show that at least 50% of CDH1 pathogenic variant carriers may not develop advanced DGC, even though, nearly 95% exhibit early DGC lesions during surveillance. Consequently, predicting disease progression is difficult, and the presence of multiple early lesions in endoscopic biopsies often leads to patient gastrectomy. We aimed to further evaluate relevant clinical findings on HDGC patients under surveillance, and identify any abnormalities associated with either early or advanced DGC.

Methods: We collected clinical data from 64 patients under follow-up at Centro Hospitalar Universitário São João (CHUSJ) that shared the same CDH1 variant (c.1901C>T). Findings from endoscopic biopsies and gastrectomy blocks were used to identify possible associations to early or advanced DGC. An extensive analysis of pathological reports was focused on H. pylori status, inflammation, and other gastric abnormalities. Outcomes of short- and long-term consequences of risk-reducing gastrectomy were further assessed from surgical intervention up until the latest clinical appointment. Females were also under surveillance for LBC, with timing of detection, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and biopsy reports analysis.

Results: From 75 tested positive carriers of the cohort, 64 were under follow-up for DGC: 10 displayed advanced DGC, 25 early DGC and 29 were asymptomatic (from which 4 had no lesions at prophylactic total gastrectomy [PTG]). The most frequent findings either at endoscopy, gastrectomy blocks or both were the presence of H. pylori in 37 individuals (~58%) and gastritis in 44 (~69%) especially frequent in asymptomatic carriers. Additionally, gastric ulcer was statistically significant in advanced DGC patients. Of the 24 asymptomatic carriers

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without previous lesions at endoscopy that performed PTG, 20 (~83%) had early DGC diagnosis after gastrectomy.

There were 30 females under surveillance at CHUSJ for LBC. From these, 7 had abnormal findings at MRI, with confirmed neoplastic lesions in 4 (~57%) at biopsy – 2 displaying LBC, and another 2 with the presence of lobular intraepithelial neoplasia (LIN). From 4 females that recurred to prophylactic mastectomy with normal MRI, only one displayed LIN.

Conclusion: This analysis highlights the low sensitivity of endoscopic surveillance at detecting early DGC lesions in asymptomatic individuals. Furthermore, no statistically significant mucosa abnormalities were identified in advanced DGC individuals except for gastric ulcer. It is important to standardize findings description in clinical reports to overcome missing information. Regarding LBC, MRI followed by biopsy revealed a high success rate in detecting lesions at an early or pre-malignant stage.

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ABSTRACT

INFORMATION

Submitted by	Gastrointestinal stromal tumours (Paula Boaventura
email	mboaventura @ipatimup.pt
Submission Objective	Abstract submitted for Preventable – Midterm Conference – October 3 2024

[GASTROINTESTINAL STROMAL TUMOURS IN CARRIERS OF RARE GERMLINE VARIANTS IN KIT/PDGFRA: AN UPDATE]

[Paula Boaventura^{1,2}; Paula Soares^{1,2,3}; Carla Oliveira^{1,2,3}

[1. IPATIMUP-Institute of Molecular Pathology and Immunology of the University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

2. i3S - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Universidade do Porto, Rua Alfredo Allen 208, 4200-135 Porto, Portugal

3. FMUP-Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto, Porto, Portugal Affiliations]

Abstract (3000 characters maximum):

Gastrointestinal stromal tumours (GISTs) are the most common mesenchymal neoplasms in adults, typically occurring after age 40, with a median age of 55-65 years, and slightly more frequent in men. Familial GISTs are rare (<5%) and often underdiagnosed. These patients develop smaller, multifocal tumours at a younger age (median 47 years) and may remain asymptomatic. Multifocal GISTs increase the risk of complications like bleeding or perforation. Familial GISTs often present with cutaneous hyperpigmentation and, less commonly, mast cell abnormalities, highlighting the need for a thorough analysis of family history.

We searched the literature and identified 53 publications reporting GISTs in carriers of rare KIT germline variants from 47 families and 9 individuals without family history. The 56 KIT carrier families/cases included 256 individuals, of whom 159 were diagnosed with GIST. Germline carriers of KIT variants often present with GISTs before age 40, with the youngest reported case diagnosed at 15 (age range: 15-82). The most common tumour site was the small intestine (93/116, 80.2%), with 45.7% (53/116) of patients having GISTs in multiple locations, mainly the stomach and small bowel. In contrast, sporadic GISTs are typically solitary and primarily located in the stomach.

Germline KIT variants in exons 13 and 17 were significantly more frequent in familial cases (19.6% and 12.5%, respectively) when compared to sporadic cases (1%). Notably, exon 17 mutations may be associated with Imatinib resistance.

Description of PDGFRA germline variants was available in seven publications, involving 5 families and 2 individuals without a family history. The families/cases carrying 7 rare germline variants included 35 individuals, of whom 11 were diagnosed with GIST. Despite the small numbers, GIST were most frequently found in the stomach (5/7, 71.4%), and the youngest case reported was 39 years of age (age range: 39-67).

The identification of germline variants in GIST families is expected to improve screening, diagnosis, follow up, prognosis and treatment of affected kindreds, so it is important to pursue its identification, allowing an early diagnosis and a more appropriated clinical management.

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ABSTRACT INFORMATION

Submitted by	Ricardo Amorim
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Submission Objective	Abstract submitted for Preventable – Midterm Conference – October 3 2024

OPTIMIZED CARE PATHWAYS AND PRICE ALLOCATION IN CDH1-ASSOCIATED HEREDITARY DIFFUSE GASTRIC CANCER

R. Amorim^{1,2}, L. Sousa^{1,3,4}, L. Garrido^{1,2,4}, S. Pereira¹, L. Moreira², M. I. Carvalho², A. Azevedo^{2,6,7}, S. Costa², M. Baptista², F. Sousa², I Gullo^{1,2,5,6}, C Dias², A. Gouveia^{2,6} and C. Oliveira^{1,4,5,6} A

1i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Universidade do Porto, Portugal

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3NIPE - Department of Economics and Economic Policies, University of Minho, Portugal

4European Reference Network on Genetic Tumour Risk Syndromes (GENTURIS)

5IPATIMUP-Instituto de Patologia e Imunologia Molecular da Universidade do Porto, Portugal

6FMUP - Faculty of Medicine, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

7ISPUP – EPIUnit, Instituto de Saúde Pública, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal

Abstract (3000 characters maximum):

Problem to be solved: Individuals born with a CDH1 loss of function variant present Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (HDGC) syndrome are likely to develop early-onset aggressive stomach cancer. Female CDH1 carriers have additional increased risk of developing breast cancer. Intensive surveillance and/or risk reduction surgery (i.e. prophylactic gastrectomy and mastectomy) prevent disease and are lifesaving management strategies. Applying structured care pathways and resource allocation can curb disease incidence or progression, delivering significant economic and societal gains. Yet, the economic management of CDH1-related HDGC remains uncharted.

Objective: Our work aims to develop a personalized cost-model for CDH1 germline variant carriers, aligning with HDGC care pathways and patient journeys, as well as to create tools for gathering health cost/price data and estimate expenses with disease prevention and treatment. **Methodology:** The HDGC care pathway, jointly developed by professionals from ERN-GENTURIS ULSSJ and experts from i3S, encompasses a comprehensive approach to HDGC patient care. This approach includes specialized care routes, clinical trajectories, as well as diagnostic, surveillance, prevention, and treatment procedures. The cost data for procedures within this pathway, aimed at serving HDGC patients at ERN-GENTURIS ULSSJ, were obtained from Portugal's Central Administration of the Health System.

Results: We have identified 7 primary modules within our framework: genetic diagnosis, cancer risk assessment and personalized recommendations, surveillance protocol, risk-reduction

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strategies, therapeutic protocols for early and advanced stage cancers, and post-treatment follow-up. These modules encompass a total of 30 clinical branches for stomach-related and 41 for breast-related procedures, tailoring diverse trajectories, including non-carriers, asymptomatic CDH1 carriers and individuals primarily diagnosed with the condition. The breakdown of these clinical branches into clinical sub-procedures, such as hospitalization for diagnosed relative groups, external consultations, and diagnostic tests, resulted in a total of 124 (stomach arm) and 147 (breast arm) different items, each with an associated cost/price.

Conclusion: We've gathered data to inform the associated costs with HDGC-related individual trajectories, crucial for crafting cost-effective strategies that boost patient outcomes and benefit the healthcare economy.

Funding: Horizon Europe PREVENTABLE (ID 101095483) www.preventable.

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ABSTRACT INFORMATION

Submitted by	Rita Barbosa-Matos
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Submission Objective	Abstract submitted for Preventable – Midterm Conference – October 3 2024

PERSONALIZED LIFETIME CANCER RISK ESTIMATES FOR AN ANCESTRAL CDH1 VARIANT

Barbosa-Matos, R.*1; Fonseca, J.*1; Garrido, L.*2; Seixas, S.1; Oliveira, R.3; Freixo, J.4; Grangeia, A.3; Pinheiro, H.1; Fernandes, S.2; Castedo, S.1; Drouet Y.5; Oliveira, C.1
i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Universidade do Porto 2CHUSJ – Centro Hospitalar e Universitário de São João 3Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto 4Center for Predictive and Preventive Genetics, Institute for Molecular and Cell Biology 5Léon Bérard Center, Lyon

Abstract (3000 characters maximum):

Background/Objectives: The CDH1 c.1901 C>T variant is the most recurrent in HDGC families across Europe, conferring susceptibility for Diffuse Gastric Cancer (DGC) and Lobular Breast Cancer (LBC). Lifetime cancer risk estimations are key for decision making toward risk-reducing gastrectomy and mastectomies in CDH1-carrier families. However, current penetrance data likely overestimate cancer risk due to combination of small families, cancer-enriched pedigree branches, different CDH1 variants, and inclusion of GC and BC cases with unknown histology.

Methods:

We collected information from nine Portuguese families (initially from 11 probands) recruited to the Centro Hospital de São João at Porto (CHUSJ) between 2000 and 2023. At least three-generation family histories and respective clinical data were collected. Anonymous pedigrees were created for 400 individuals across all families. For 285 individuals (9 probands; 276 relatives), information on cancer status, histology, and age of last news (age at last follow-up, risk-reduction surgery, cancer diagnosis or death) were collected. Cumulative risks of DGC and LBC were calculated relative to regional cancer incidence data using the genotype restricted likelihood (GRL) method. For each phenotype, age nodes were delineated by the age distribution of the cohort, encompassing carriers and individuals with unknown genotypes.

Results: Among 285 individuals, 95 were CDH1 carriers, 26 had gastric cancer before age 60, and 12 had breast cancer. This is the first lifetime cancer-risk study to consider DGC and LBC estimated incidence for a particular geographical region. Moreover, cumulative, and relative risks for DGC were estimated including both early and advanced cancer cases, or advanced DGC only. Our cumulative risk for Advanced DGC and LBC was estimated at 8.8% by age 60.

Conclusion: This is the largest cohort ever studied for a specific CDH1 variant present in a population sharing the same geographical area for centuries. Despite disease expressivity and early-onset of cancer being similar to families described worldwide, our data challenges all previous GC and BC risk estimations for CDH1 carriers. Our results found lower DGC and LBC

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cumulative risks, underscoring important considerations that cause artificially high estimates. Lack of specific information on cancer histology, regional population cancer incidence and accounting for early lesions identified during prophylactic treatment can bias outcome in CDH1 carriers and should be considered for future studies.

Instructions

- Your abstract should include: Problem to be solved; Objective; Methodology; Results; and Conclusion
- Define all non-standard abbreviations at first use;
- No figures or tables can be included;
- An additional section for acknowledgements can be added to the body (included in the character count)

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ABSTRACT INFORMATION

Submitted by	Sara B. Pereira
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Submission Objective	Abstract submitted for Preventable – Midterm Conference – October 3 2024

[PREVENTABLE - CANCER PREVENTION VS CANCER TREATMENT: THE RARE TUMOUR RISK SYNDROMES BATTLE]

[Sara B. Pereira 1*, Liliana Sousa 1*, Ricardo Amorim 1, PREVENTABLE Consortium 2, Carla Oliveira 1,2,3,5]

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Abstract (3000 characters maximum):

Problem to be solved:

Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes (RTRS) are rare diseases (≤ 5 per 10.000 people) caused by heritable genetic variants that confer a lifetime risk of developing cancers, usually aggressive, as high as 100%. Although RTRS provide a unique context for cancer prevention and intensive surveillance and risk reduction surgery of healthy carriers has shown to be effective, most healthcare organizations still prioritize the treatment of symptomatic RTRS patients. Thus, it is urgent to demonstrate the cost-benefit of prevention in RTRS.

Objective:

The PREVENTABLE project, funded by Horizon Europe, was created to bridge the knowledge gap on the cost-efficiency and clinical outcomes of prevention vs. treatment in eight RTRS. Our ambition is to demonstrate the social and financial benefits of prevention, not only for patients, but also for healthcare providers and society in general.

Methodology:

The PREVENTABLE consortium, led by i3S, is using an unprecedented approach that merges specialized clinical knowledge on RTRS, including HDGC, real-life clinical data and experiences from professionals and patients, with health economic models and social sciences to estimate the cost-benefit of risk-reduction interventions in these syndromes. This approach will also allow to delineate guidelines for communication between clinical teams and patients.

Results:

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We initiated by generating RTRS-specific matrix matching individual patients' trajectories (pathways of care) and respective clinical procedures. The matrices were used to develop an IT tool for the systematic registration of real patients' clinical data into the condition-specific pathways of care and collection of healthcare consumption costs/prices. At the moment, the IT tool for HDGC is finalized and data collection is ongoing. The data collected will allow a patient-centred cost-effectiveness analysis, based on real-life clinical data, to demonstrate the value of preventive care in RTRS patients. In parallel, surveys and focus groups are being implemented to identify the factors that influence care pathways choices for RTRS carriers/patients and their clinical teams. The strengths, weaknesses, obstacles and threats of RTRS care pathways are also being assessed and educational outreach material for RTRS-related knowledge, including patients and clinicians testimonials, is being produced.

Conclusion/Future perspectives:

The results obtained will be delivered to a diversity of stakeholders, including policymakers, in order to promote the implementation of cost-effective RTRS patient-centred care in Europe.

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